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Estimation of Chromate Ions in presence of various Oxy-anions by Polarographic Method

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KOLTHOFF Gregor¹ determined chromate ions amperometrically by titrating it with barium ions in presence of various percentage of ethanol, which lowers the solubility of barium chromate. The present paper presents the results of the polarographic determination of chromate ions in presence of arsenate, arsenite, molybdate, tungstate, bromate, selenate & tellurate ions.

Experimental

Solutions containing various concentration of chromate ions (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 mM) were prepared in presence of 0.1M concentration of various oxy-anions containing 0.1M NaOH. The above solutions were also prepared in absence of sodium hydroxide and it was observed that in absence of NaOH the reduction waves either contained maxima or ill defined and thus the results were not useful from analytical aspect. The polarograms were recorded on Radiometer P O4 automatically after deaeration for 20 min by bubbling purified nitrogen. The blank polarograms of various oxy-anions in 0.1M NaOH were also recorded to choose the suitability of oxy-anions. All the measurements were carried out at 30°C which was maintained with Haake type ultra thermostat. Electrolysis was carried out in a conventional H-type cell with a agar-agar plug saturated with KCl. The dropping mercury electrode having $m = 1.1464$ mg/sec. and $t = 5$ sec. (at 50 cm of mercury pressure in 0.1M NaOH with applied potential of -1.0 V vs S. C. E.) was used for all the measurements.

Results and Discussion

(i) *Reduction of chromate ions in presence of molybdate ions*: Investigations were carried out in 0.1M molybdate having 0.1M NaOH. Chromate ion produces a single well defined polarographic wave in presence of 0.1M molybdate ions containing 0.1M sodium hydroxide. The i_x was found to increase with increase of chromate ion concentration where as half wave potential remained constant. The plots of i_x vs chromate ion concentration was linear and pass through original. This shows that the reduction of chromate ions is diffusion controlled in presence of 0.1M molybdate in strongly alkaline media. Thus small amount of chromate ions can be determined in excess of molybdate ions. The results have been summarised in Table 1.

(ii) *Reduction of chromate ions in presence of tungstate ions*: In presence of 0.1M tungstate containing 0.1M NaOH, chromate ions produce two reduction waves. The first wave being small and contained a round maxima where as the second wave was found to be well developed having no maxima. Thus the second wave is useful for its determination. Attempts to suppress the maxima for the first reduction wave was not successful with gelatin (0.01%) or triton X₁₀₀

TABLE I—CONCENTRATION OF CHROMATE IONS (MM)

Supporting electrolyte	0.5 E _{1/2}	I _d	I _d / C	1.0 E _{1/2}	I _d	I _d / C	1.5 E _{1/2}	I _d	I _d / C	2.0 E _{1/2}	I _d	I _d / C
	(-V vs S.C.E.)	(μA)		(-V vs S.C.E.)	(μA)		(-V vs S.C.E.)	(μA)		(-V vs S.C.E.)	(μA)	
Molybdate	1.085	5.58	11.0	1.090	11.00	11.00	1.080	16.50	11.00	1.080	22.00	11.00
Tungstate	1.080	4.25	8.50	1.080	8.50	8.50	1.080	12.75	8.50	1.080	17.00	8.50
Selenate	1.085	5.00	10.00	1.090	9.75	9.75	1.080	15.00	10.00	1.080	20.00	10.00
Bromate	1.070	5.75	11.50	1.080	11.25	11.25	1.080	17.00	11.30	1.080	22.50	11.20
Arsenate	1.080	9.50	19.00	1.080	18.75	18.75	1.080	28.50	19.00	1.080	38.00	19.00
Arsenite	1.080	4.50	9.00	1.085	9.05	9.05	1.080	13.60	9.06	1.080	18.00	9.00

(0.005%), the second wave became stretched and ill defined in presence of these surface active substance. Thus the second wave is useful for its determination without surface active substance. The results have been summarised in Table 1.

(iii) *Reduction in presence of selenate ions*: With 0.1M NaOH, chromate ion produces a well developed reduction wave in presence of 0.1 M selenate ions. From the measurements of i_d vs chromate ion concentration, it is evident that the chromate can be estimated in excess of selenate ions in alkaline solutions. Results are recorded in Table 1.

(iv) *Reduction in presence of bromate ions*: In presence of 0.1M NaOH containing 0.1M bromate ions, chromate ion produces a single well defined reduction wave. The plots of i_d vs concentration of chromate ions come to linear which shows that the current is limited by diffusion. The results have been incorporated in Table 1.

(v) *Reduction of chromate ions in presence of arsenate ions*: A single well defined wave was occurred for reduction of chromate ions in presence of 0.1M arsenate ions having 0.1M NaOH. From the plots of i_d vs chromate ions concentration, it is evident that the chromate ions can be estimated in presence of arsenate ions in alkaline medium. The results have been summarised in table 1.

(vi) *Reduction of chromate ions in presence of arsenite ions*: In freshly prepared solution, by mixing arsenite ions & chromate ions in 0.1M NaOH, two reduction waves were obtained. The first wave contained a maximum, whose height increases with increase of chromate ion concentration. This maximum could not be suppressed by addition of large amount of gelatin (0.01%) which deforms the second wave, which is well developed in absence of gelatin. Thus second wave is of analytical use. The results have been summarised in table 1. On keeping the solution it turns bluish-green and the diffusion current decreases with time. Thus chromate ions can be estimated only in freshly prepared arsenite solution in alkaline media.

(vii) *Reduction of chromate ions in presence of tellurate ions*: In alkaline media, chromate ion produces a single reduction wave with a sharp maximum in presence of tellurate ions. The height of the maximum increases with chromate ion concentration. Attempts to suppress this maximum, so that it can be of analytical importance were not successful, even 0.01% of gelatin could not suppress the maximum.

From the above results, it is obvious that small amounts of chromate ions can be determined in excess of molybdate, tungstate, selenate, bromate, arsenate, arsenite & tellurate in alkaline media. However, in presence of arsenite ions, freshly prepared solutions should be used. The attempts to determine chromate ions in presence of tellurate ions was not useful due to non suppression of maximum.

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Solvent Extraction of Cobalt (II) with a Mixture of Thenoyltrifluoroacetone and Ethylmethylketone in Benzene from acetate Buffers.

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EXTRACTIVE separations of various metal ions from alkaline as well as from acid media using ethylmethylketone (EMK) have been reported^{1,2,3}. It has been observed that the solubility of various metal chelates in EMK is greater than in inert solvents, which is due to the higher dielectric constant of the ketone. Its antisnergistic properties have also been observed⁴, but synergism with EMK in combination with thenoyltrifluoroacetone (HTTA) has not been investigated.

In the present studies, extraction of cobalt (II) from an aqueous acetate medium into a benzene solution of a mixture of thenoyltrifluoroacetone (HTTA) and ethylmethylketone [EMK] has been studied. The formation of the monoadduct and its conversion into the diadduct have been observed. These studies include the efficiency of the extraction of cobalt (II), the composition of the complexes transferred to the organic phase, and the extraction constant for the synergic reaction.

Experimental

Experiments were carried out in a similar manner as described in the previous papers^{5,6}.

When experimental conditions are chosen so as to avoid interference from possible side reactions, the synergistic parameters^{7,8} are reduced to three: (i) the concentration of the hydrogen ion in the aqueous solution, (ii) that of the chelating acid and (iii) the neutral ligand in the organic phase. Under these conditions, the value of the extraction constant K , and the composition⁹ of the synergistic adduct formed during the extractive transfer of the metal from an aqueous solution, can be calculated with the help of the results of log-log plots of the distribution ratio against one of the three synergistic parameters, keeping the other two constant.

Results and Discussion

The plot of $\log [Co (TTA)_n EMK_r]_{org} / [Co]_{org}$ against pH for different values of $[EMK]_{org}$ are nearly parallel and at any given pH the distribution coefficient, q , increases with the concentration of EMK present. Thus the system shows the phenomenon of synergism; in the absence of HTTA the extraction of cobalt by a solution of EMK in benzene is negligible. It has been observed that the number of liberated protons is 2; showing thereby that two molecules of HTTA react with cobalt (II) to release two protons.

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